

A combination method for response of irregular buildings under simultaneous action of two horizontal components of earthquake motion

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Abstract. The ground motion caused by an earthquake can be considered as the resultant of three orthogonal translation components along three Cartesian coordinates x , y , and z ; and three rotational components about these three co-ordinate axes. Though it is well recognized that the response of important structures like nuclear reactor components, dams, tall buildings, asymmetric buildings and long-span bridges, may be dependent on all the three translational components of motion, but due to the complexity of the three-dimensional analysis and various uncertainties in spatial combination procedures, most of the studies considered only one component of earthquake motion. Many investigators have recognized the necessity of finding the response of structures under multi-component earthquake excitation however, the methods for such analysis cannot be applied directly to irregular structures without well-defined principal axes. In the present study, a simple three-dimensional irregular steel moment-resisting single-storey building is analysed to propose a combination rule for simultaneous action of two components of horizontal excitation. Numerical analysis based on geometric mean response spectrum [SAGM] is compared with the principal directional response spectrum [SAXP] and critical response spectrum [SACRIT]. Dynamic analysis of the building is performed using CSI SAP2000. Based on the comprehensive analysis of the response of the selected simple building has revealed that the SRSS of the response due to two horizontal components of excitation applied in any two arbitrary orthogonal direction provides an adequate combination rule for such irregular buildings.

Keywords: Response Spectrum Analysis, Principal Response Spectrum, Critical Response Spectrum IS:1893(2016), Asymmetric Building, SAP2000.

1 Introduction

The ground motion caused by an earthquake can be considered as the resultant of three orthogonal translation components along three cartesian coordinates x , y , and z ; and three rotational components about these co-ordinate axes. Many investigators have recognized the necessity of finding the response of structures under multi-component earthquake excitation. Bolotin [1] presented a stochastic theory of structural response to multi-component seismic loading. Penzien et al. [2] pointed out the importance of finding the response caused by three translational components of earthquake motion and studied the characteristics of three-dimensional ground motion.

Chen [3] investigated the statistical dependence of the three components of ground motion. Rosenblueth et al. [4] developed an approximate procedure for combining the response component. They expressed the resultant response as a linear combination of the components of the interest and found the coefficient of expansion so that the error is minimized. Wilson et al. [5] Presented a method for three-dimensional dynamic analysis for multi-component earthquake spectra.

Other works suggest the methods of combining the maxima of the three components of the response, where each of the components maxima is found by the customary modal superposition methods using response spectra of the corresponding ground acceleration component. Chu et al. [6] have suggested the square root of the sum of the squares (SRSS) method for finding the resultant of three partial responses. The USNRC [7] recommends this method for combining three special responses. The [Max+30%] method suggested by Resenblueth et al. [4] is recommended by ATC-3(1978) Provisions. In this method, the resultant is taken as the maximum components plus 30% of the sum of all other components.

Anagnostopoulos [8] has made a comparative study of different modal and spatial combination method. In addition to SRSS and [Max+30%] rules, he compared the methods, viz SUM, SRLS and their averages with SRSS. He has also used the [Max+40%] and [Max+50%] components, whereas in NRLS method resultant is defined as the maximum of three-component plus the SRSS of the other two. This was suggested as a modal superposition method by O'Hara et al. [9].

Hadjian [10] shown that the common spatial combination rules like SRSS and [Max+30%] have been derived on the assumption of statistical independence between components of the response, though such assumption may not always be justified. Anagnostopoulos [8] has shown that because of the correlation between components of earthquake motion, additive response effects are created in corner members of the three-dimensional structure. Moreover, all the above-mentioned spatial combination rules combine the maxima of the components responses to get the maximum of the resultant, whereas the component maxima do not occur at the same time.

Haluk et al. [11], considered the spectrum intensity concept investigate the bi-directional effects of earthquakes and the effectiveness of spectrum intensity method. In the study proposed by Haluk et al. [11] vertical component of the ground motion was excluded, assuming that horizontal components are the governing components for

building analysis. However, the vertical component can be included in a similar way, when the principal component is in the vertical direction. Lopez et al. [13] investigated the response of a regular elastic building for 3 components of ground motion using complete quadratic combination with 3 components (CQC3). In the paper presented by Kote et al. [14], investigated the response of a typical 6 story steel building for [Max+30%] rule, Principal directional response spectrum and critical response spectrum, and it has been found that response obtained by [MAX+30%] rule underestimated when compared with the desired response in principal directional response spectrum [SAXP] and critical response spectrum [SACRIT]. It has been also discussed that in no case the maximum response shall exceed the response obtained by the critical response spectrum. Thus, provides the upper bound to the multi-directional component response.

All the foregoing methods can be applied only if the building under consideration has two principal axes in two perpendicular directions, no widely accepted method exists for estimating the response of irregular buildings with no principal axes. When the excitation is applied in the two orthogonal directions, for a building with two distinct directions (x and y) the different combination rules are available in the literature for computation of the maximum response in two perpendicular directions of the building, however no combination rule is available to get the maximum response of irregular buildings under simultaneously excited loads. In the present paper, two components of ground motion are applied in the two orthogonal directions and detailed investigation are carried out to suggest a combination rule for such buildings by computing the response under several different ground excitation with widely differing characteristics. we have estimated the response in each element of a simple example irregular building by considering the geometric mean response spectrum [SAGM], principal response spectrum [SAXP] and critical response spectrum [SACRIT] of the three real accelerograms.

Estimation for the maximum response in the local directions of each element of the building using combination rule like higher of the response under two components of excitation [Max], Higher response + 30% of the lower response [Max + 30%] and square root of sum of squares [SRSS] of the two components of response under two components of excitation. As the irregular building doesn't have any principal axes, all the three response quantities have been estimated and compared for all possible non-redundant direction of ground motion. It has been found that the SRSS method of combination under two simultaneous ground motion is a suitable and direction independent method to combine response to design the individual elements of the building.

2 Particulars of the building

A simple single-bay single-storey frame is considered for the present study is shown in Figure 1. The building has 4 steel columns ISLB 200 and supports 150mm thick R.C.C. slab. The orientation of the steel columns is shown in Figure 1. The building is analyzed for dead load intensity of 2.5 kN/m² acting on the slab. The damping ratio considered for the building is 5%. The time period (s) for the building for the 3 modes of vibration are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Modal analysis results

Mode [No.]	Description	Time Period [sec]	Natural frequency [rad/s]
1	Translation in x direction	0.4001	15.7041
2	Torsion (rotation about z axis)	0.1305	48.1489
3	Translation in y direction	0.1191	52.7450

(1a) – 3D building isometric view

(1b) - Plan

Fig. 1. A simple single bay single storey irregular steel building considered for analysis
 [Note:- CM – Center of Mass and CR – Center of Rigidity]

3 Input Excitation

To perform the numerical analysis, Response spectra of the three real earthquake records are used. The details of the considered earthquakes are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Details of the selected earthquakes.

EQ [#]	Name of Earthquake	Date	Moment Magnitude [M]	Focal Depth [km]	Epicentre distance [km]	Peak Ground Accel [g]	Recording Station
1	Gorkha Nepal	25/04/2015	7.9	13.4	13.6	0.754	Kirtipur
2	Sikkim	18/09/2011	6.7	10.00	50.3	0.569	Gangtok
3	Uttarkashi	20/10/1991	6.9	13.2	73.9	1.083	Bhatwari

Three different types of response spectra considered for analysis are as follows.

3.1 Geometric Mean response spectrum [SAGM]

The geometric mean response spectra [SAGM] of the two horizontal components of ground motion record is computed using equation (1).

$$SAGM = \sqrt[2]{SA_x \cdot SA_y} \quad (1)$$

Where, SA_x = Response spectrum of an SDOF system for ground motion in x-direction
 SA_y = Response spectrum of an SDOF system for ground motion in y-direction

3.2 Response Spectrum in Major Principal Direction [SAXP]

The response spectrum in the major principal direction [SAXP] is obtained by resolving the components of the original accelerogram record in the major principal direction. Equation (2) Gives the symmetric correlation coefficient matrix used to determine the direction of major and minor principal ground motion.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{xx} & \sigma_{xy} \\ \sigma_{yx} & \sigma_{yy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where the σ_{xx} is the normalised correlation coefficient of the acceleration ground motion in the x-direction, σ_{yy} is the normalised correlation coefficient of the acceleration ground motion in the y-direction and σ_{xy} is normalized cross-correlation coefficient of the acceleration ground motion. These correlation coefficients are obtained as per equation (3), (4) and (5) respectively.

$$\sigma_{xx} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T a_{x(t)}^2 dt \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma_{xx} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T a_{x(t)}^2 dt \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{xy} = \sigma_{yx} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T a_{x(t)} a_{y(t)} dt \quad (5)$$

we know that the cross-correlation coefficients for major and minor principal directions are always zero, therefore, symmetric correlation coefficient matrix as given in equation (2) is diagonalized by solving the eigenvalue problem for the eigenvalues (λ_1 and λ_2) and corresponding eigenvectors $\{\phi\}_1$ and $\{\phi\}_2$ gives the direction of the major and minor principal acceleration ground motion.

Corresponding to the eigenvectors of this transformed new diagonalised matrix gives the directions of major principal ground motion (θ_1) and minor principle (θ_2). Directions for major principal and minor principal ground motion are computed from the equation (6).

$$\theta_1 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\phi_{(2,1)}}{\phi_{(1,1)}} \right) \text{ and } \theta_2 = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\phi_{(2,2)}}{\phi_{(1,2)}} \right) \quad (6)$$

The ground motion in the major principal direction (θ_1) is computed from equation (7).

$$a_{p1(t)} = a_{x(t)} \cos(\theta_1) + a_{y(t)} \sin(\theta_1) \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Principal directional acceleration ground motion

3.3 Critical Response Spectrum [SACRIT]

Critical Response Spectrum is obtained by the resultant response $R(t)$ of an SDOF system obtained from SRSS of the response in the x-direction $R_{x(t)}$ and response in the y-direction $R_{y(t)}$ for each natural period (T) and damping ratio (ξ). The resultant response of an SDOF system is computed by equation (8). Figure 3 shows the graphical representation of the response of an SDOF system under the simultaneous action of excitation in x and y-direction.

$$SA_{crit(T,\xi)} = R(t)_{max} \tag{8}$$

Where,

$$R(t) = \sqrt{R_{x(t)}^2 + R_{y(t)}^2} \tag{9}$$

Fig. 3. Absolute acceleration response of an SDOF system under two orthogonal directional excitation.

The spectra for the three selected earthquake records with computed geometric mean response spectrum [SAXP], Major principal directional response Spectrum [SAXP] and Critical response spectrum [SACRIT] are shown in Figure 4.

(4a) Response spectrum of Nepal Earthquake

(4b) Response spectrum of Sikkim Earthquake

(4c) Response spectrum of Uttarkashi Earthquake

Fig. 4. Earthquake Response Spectra

4 Numerical analysis and result

For the example building shown in Figure (1), the response is dependent upon the direction of the application of excitation. For the purpose of illustration numerical analysis is first carried out for critical response spectrum in the two orthogonal x and y direction and response for maximum element shear force and maximum element moments in the local axis of member are obtained. To find directional dependence of the response, excitation is applied at an interval of 5° w.r.t previous directions of application of excitation. Results for the Maximum shear force due to two orthogonal directions response due to two orthogonal excitation using [Max], [Max+30%] rule and [SRSS] rule are shown in Figure 5. Similar results for maximum moments are shown in Figure 6.

(5a) Maximum shear force in local 'u' direction

(5b) Maximum shear force in local 'v' direction

Fig. 5. Max Shear force in column.

(6c) Maximum moment in column about local 'u' direction

(6d) Maximum moment in column about local 'v' direction

Fig. 6. Max Bending moment in column.

From Figure 5 and 6 it can be seen that the maximum response computed from [Max], [Max+30%] rule are varying with respect to the angle of application of dynamic load. Hence to find the maximum response we need to analyze the building for input excitation aligned in different directions. However, SRSS response is seen to be directional independence and is closed to higher estimated [Max+30%] response. It is thus proposed that this rule of combination can be used conveniently to estimate the response of irregular building under simultaneous excitation in any two arbitrary selected

orthogonal directions of motion. Using SRSS rule design forces are computed for each element for the response spectra shown in Figure 4. The results for design shear force, bending moment and displacement of joints are given in Table 3, 4 and 5.

Table 3. Design Shear Force in Columns by SRSS rule.

Earth-quake	Excita-tion	Shear Force in column [kN] (local 'u' direction)				Shear Force in column [kN] (local 'v' direction)			
		A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Nepal	SAGM	0.748	0.748	1.473	1.473	1.530	1.530	1.640	1.640
	SAXP	0.797	0.797	1.571	1.571	1.574	1.574	1.688	1.688
	SACRIT	0.909	0.909	1.793	1.793	1.712	1.712	1.835	1.835
Sikkim	SAGM	0.352	0.352	0.672	0.672	1.705	1.705	1.833	1.833
	SAXP	0.493	0.493	0.950	0.950	2.092	2.092	2.247	2.247
	SACRIT	0.495	0.495	0.950	0.950	2.148	2.148	2.308	2.308
Ut-tarkashi	SAGM	0.859	0.859	1.685	1.685	2.309	2.309	2.479	2.479
	SAXP	0.994	0.994	1.953	1.953	2.280	2.280	2.446	2.446
	SACRIT	1.011	1.011	1.983	1.983	2.660	2.660	2.855	2.855

Table 4. Design Moments in Columns by SRSS rule.

Earth-quake	Excita-tion	Bending Moment in column [kNm] (about local 'u' direction)				Bending Moment in column [kNm] (about local 'v' direction)			
		A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Nepal	SAGM	2.095	2.095	2.323	2.323	1.120	1.120	2.179	2.179
	SAXP	2.160	2.160	2.395	2.395	1.193	1.193	2.324	2.324
	SACRIT	2.341	2.341	2.596	2.596	1.362	1.362	2.652	2.652
Sikkim	SAGM	2.348	2.348	2.606	2.606	0.528	0.528	0.994	0.994
	SAXP	2.881	2.881	3.198	3.198	0.738	0.738	1.405	1.405
	SACRIT	2.953	2.953	3.279	3.279	0.741	0.741	1.405	1.405
Ut-tarkashi	SAGM	3.172	3.172	3.520	3.520	1.287	1.287	2.491	2.491
	SAXP	3.117	3.117	3.459	3.459	1.489	1.489	2.888	2.888
	SACRIT	3.652	3.652	4.052	4.052	1.514	1.514	2.933	2.933

Table 5. Column displacement at joints by SRSS rule.

Earth-quake	Excita-tion	Column displacement at joints [mm] (in Global 'x' direction)				Column displacement at joints [mm] (in Global 'y' direction)			
		A	B	C	D	A	B	C	D
Nepal	SAGM	6.195	6.195	12.690	12.690	3.491	3.491	6.705	6.705
	SAXP	6.595	6.595	13.535	13.535	3.715	3.715	7.141	7.141
	SACRIT	7.532	7.532	15.447	15.447	4.207	4.207	8.136	8.136
Sikkim	SAGM	2.951	2.951	5.777	5.777	2.019	2.019	3.352	3.352
	SAXP	4.102	4.102	8.168	8.168	2.700	2.700	4.617	4.617
	SACRIT	4.135	4.135	8.168	8.168	2.711	2.711	4.638	4.638
Ut-tarkashi	SAGM	7.126	7.126	14.504	14.504	4.173	4.173	7.779	7.779
	SAXP	8.253	8.253	16.821	16.821	4.685	4.685	8.936	8.936
	SACRIT	8.389	8.389	17.077	17.077	4.889	4.889	9.146	9.146

It is seen that due to symmetry about the y-axis, the design shear forces and design Moments in column A, B and C, D are identical. It is seen that Results obtained by geometric mean response spectrum [SAGM] are lower when compared with Major principal directional response spectrum [SAXP] and Critical response spectrum [SACRIT]. As observed Critical response spectrum [SACRIT] gives the highest response in the columns. It is therefore recommended that the design may be based on the maximum response under critical response spectrum to be used to ensure adequate safety for design in view of the uncertainties in the directions of ground motion w.r.t orientation of the building.

5 Conclusion

After the detailed illustration, the major conclusions are summarized as following.

1. For a building with two distinct directions x and y, the different combination rules are available in the literature for computation of the maximum response in two perpendicular directions of the building. However, no combination rule is available to get the maximum response of irregular buildings under simultaneously excited loads.
2. Irregular buildings don't have any principal axes, hence the response quantities based on the [Max], [Max+30%] rule and [SRSS] rule have been computed and results are compared for all possible non-redundant direction of ground motion. It has been found that the SRSS method of combination under the action of two simultaneous ground motion is a suitable and direction independent method to determine the maximum response in the elements of the building.
3. The geometric mean response spectrum [SAGM] gives lower estimates of response when compared with the major principal directional response spectrum [SAXP] and critical response spectrum [SACRIT].
4. It is recommended to design the elements of the buildings for design forces based on the critical response spectrum [SACRIT] to ensure adequate safety in view of the uncertainties in the directions of ground motion w.r.t. the orientation of the building.
5. In the present study, a simple single-bay single-storey irregular building is considered for computation of response due to the simultaneous action of two components of ground motion. However, it is expected to be applicable to multistoried irregular buildings.

References

1. Bolotin, V. V.: Structural Response of the Multi-component Seismic Loading considered as a Non-Stationary Random Process. Proc. of the first Chilean session on Seismology and Earthquake Engineering, Santiago (1963).
2. Penzien J and Watae M.: Characteristics of three-dimensional earthquake ground motion. Journal of Earthquake Engineering and structural dynamics. Vol 3, pp. 365-373 (1975).
3. Chen C.: Definition of Statistically Independent Time Histories. Journal of Structural Division ASCE, Paper-101, pp. 449-451 (1975).
4. Rosenblueth E and Contreras H.: Approximate Design for Multi-Component. Earthquake Journal of Engineering Mechanics Division, ASCE. Paper-103, pp. 881-893 (1977).

5. Wilson E. L. and Button M.R.: Three-Dimensional dynamic analysis for multi-component Earthquake Spectra. *Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics*. Vol-10, pp. 471-479 (1982).
6. Chu S.L., Amin. M. and Singh S.: Special treatment of actions of three earthquakes components on structures. *Nuclear Engineering and Design*. Vol-21, pp. 126-316 (1972)
7. U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission: Combining Modal Responses and Spatial components in Seismic Response Analysis. Regulatory Guide 192, Revision-1, Washington D. C. (1973)
8. Anagnostopoulos S.A.: Response Spectrum Techniques for Three-Component Earthquake Design. *Journal of Earthquake Engineering and structural dynamics*, Vol- 9, pp. 459-476 (1981).
9. O'Hara G.J. and Cunnif P.F.: Elements of Normal Mode Theory- NRL Report 6002. U.S. Naval Research Laboratory, Washington D.C. (1953)
10. Hadjian A.H.: On the Correlation of the components of strong ground motion. Proc 2nd International Conference on Micro-zonation San Francisco, Vol-3, pp. 1199-1120 (1978).
11. Haluk S. Oguz C.C., Feridun C.: Review and evaluation of combination rules for structures under bi-directional earthquake excitations. 13th World Conference on Earthquake Engineering, pp. 2079 (2004).
12. Gupta I. D. and M. D. Trifunac: Order Statistics of Peaks of the Response to multi-component seismic excitation. *Bull. Ind. Soc. Earthquake Tech.*, Vol-258, pp. 135-259 (1987).
13. Lopez O. A, Anil K. Chopra and Julio J. Hernandez: Adapting the CQC3 Rule for Three Seismic Components with Different Spectra. *Journal of Structural Engineering ASCE*, Pap-130, pp. 403-410 (2004).
14. Kote P. B., Madhekar S.N., Gupta I. D.: Investigation of 30% rule for the combination of component response with the unidirectional principal response spectrum. Proceedings of the 4th Indian Conference on Applied Mechanics, pp. 819- 825 (2019).